

Circle packing inside a regular octagon: supplemental material

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Abstract

We report the configurations of $2 \leq N \leq 200$ congruent disks packed inside a regular octagon obtained using the algorithms of ref. [1].

1 Introduction

We report here the densest configurations for circle packing inside a regular octagon obtained using the algorithms described in ref. [1] for $2 \leq N \leq 200$. Although we cannot claim that the configurations that we have reached correspond to global maxima of the packing fraction, we believe that they should provide good lower bounds. Such bounds may be improved in the future, either by performing more intensive numerical calculations or by coming up with more efficient algorithms. The reader is advised to refer to [1] for a description of the algorithms and a discussion of previous work.

This document is organized as follows: in section 2 we display the densest configurations of N congruent disks packed inside a regular octagon, for $2 \leq N \leq 200$; in section 3 we display the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations previously found. The data corresponding to the configurations reported in this document may be found at the repository [2] or directly from the author.

2 Densest configurations found for $N \leq 200$

The configurations are plotted assigning a color code described in [1], which depends on the number of contacts of each disk. Since the calculation is numerical, this information has to be assessed within a given tolerance: in our case, if the distance between two disks exceeds by 10^{-6} the minimal distance among any two disks in the configuration, they are regarded as being in contact. Refinement is typically a slow process and it could be demanding when N is

large: configurations with a large number of black disks (i.e. disks that are not in contact with any other disk or with the walls of the container) are most likely improvable upon performing a suitable refinement.

Table 1: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular octagon for $2 \leq N \leq 79$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
2	0.468245218314	0.503437279335	41	0.12940287354	0.788207152538
3	0.428969548413	0.633786312846	42	0.128410781423	0.795098514256
4	0.380581895389	0.6651581467	43	0.126792802209	0.793645082748
5	0.34184693223	0.670813898228	44	0.125772083516	0.799079264531
6	0.314167684366	0.679896720383	45	0.124817223995	0.8048783144
7	0.308425907488	0.764484028117	46	0.122806228708	0.796466098768
8	0.292853112904	0.787695474599	47	0.120996735722	0.789975895333
9	0.254822558167	0.670945007893	48	0.119710199244	0.789718330176
10	0.243931374794	0.683131011142	49	0.118425521992	0.788960697762
11	0.237517122658	0.712444775414	50	0.117440216282	0.791721361823
12	0.228353523658	0.718398397483	51	0.11623574519	0.791076090272
13	0.222092931626	0.736175737109	52	0.114997642309	0.789495921029
14	0.214636889499	0.740466545042	53	0.113946428756	0.790034360366
15	0.206627612425	0.73525273368	54	0.113101602664	0.793048871887
16	0.199792679302	0.733242785447	55	0.112128725865	0.793898786036
17	0.19445002848	0.737961351348	56	0.111073974303	0.793197476595
18	0.191466926357	0.757580365076	57	0.110119024575	0.793538936623
19	0.18792059899	0.770319782357	58	0.109333982746	0.795988887283
20	0.182622215241	0.765783285064	59	0.108587279654	0.798690634775
21	0.180355045441	0.784232003098	60	0.107799255808	0.800481777134
22	0.176438418982	0.786280798029	61	0.106893699433	0.800207696489
23	0.169990525572	0.763037607195	62	0.106041125441	0.800403575702
24	0.166584175761	0.764623082298	63	0.105413122319	0.803708530389
25	0.162741103626	0.760156819931	64	0.104582264409	0.803645893201
26	0.159744194564	0.761714441912	65	0.103684912196	0.802256342072
27	0.15645426431	0.758764926361	66	0.102950993599	0.803107523352
28	0.154724984954	0.769569068234	67	0.102293120028	0.804889620452
29	0.152728780845	0.776619769802	68	0.101434263986	0.803243003082
30	0.149156265431	0.76625431042	69	0.10070238006	0.803336009702
31	0.14720987258	0.771266097138	70	0.100051136746	0.804471695531
32	0.145041181714	0.772860855243	71	0.0994985399584	0.806975665211
33	0.143043653236	0.77521077427	72	0.0987871566941	0.806681582708
34	0.140883472177	0.774760880668	73	0.0982885963831	0.80965089503
35	0.139632414239	0.783446261125	74	0.097776341547	0.812209304744
36	0.137786873891	0.784669674634	75	0.097174336403	0.813079674036
37	0.135923616742	0.784802254495	76	0.0965876286649	0.814001628501
38	0.134107351038	0.784616503677	77	0.0958457618881	0.81209199031
39	0.133041901769	0.79251988801	78	0.0950765362201	0.809487187739
40	0.131167969569	0.790103993671	79	0.0945053861318	0.810044517491

Table 2: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular octagon for $80 \leq N \leq 161$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
80	0.0937483117609	0.807208213173	121	0.0767238053532	0.817738252728
81	0.0931341862778	0.806625489516	122	0.0764511740309	0.818647279181
82	0.0926404048099	0.807948007995	123	0.076092310273	0.81762719033
83	0.09216021269	0.809345027831	124	0.0758003153934	0.817960599201
84	0.0915069886793	0.807525950309	125	0.0754836425019	0.817681901299
85	0.0909248075041	0.806774903731	126	0.0752005489955	0.818052622609
86	0.0905274362147	0.809147259087	127	0.0748787771941	0.817503991816
87	0.0899667644985	0.808448073969	128	0.0746709210004	0.819373019976
88	0.0894979355866	0.809240074734	129	0.0743254070983	0.818150080478
89	0.0889932866891	0.809232233416	130	0.0741042595614	0.819593245627
90	0.0885544615903	0.810274323901	131	0.0737900923604	0.818909817024
91	0.0880121979055	0.809274394543	132	0.0734450766803	0.817462769508
92	0.0875669274699	0.809909931141	133	0.073207646106	0.818338908889
93	0.087184458216	0.811577070937	134	0.0729629973158	0.818990388928
94	0.0868117176315	0.813304594599	135	0.0727747346244	0.820849812438
95	0.0863215118056	0.812700177951	136	0.0724875825982	0.820417311035
96	0.0859001447229	0.813256790059	137	0.0722093974338	0.820118640236
97	0.0854628816478	0.813383714625	138	0.0719773581102	0.820804189435
98	0.0850402259032	0.813661112168	139	0.071782122693	0.822273071538
99	0.084649688582	0.814431566186	140	0.0714950154561	0.821576934997
100	0.0841961012468	0.813865496775	141	0.0712602234764	0.822019550192
101	0.0837556110304	0.813425663697	142	0.0710030914593	0.82188590913
102	0.0834214510659	0.814937542647	143	0.0708074241509	0.823118386662
103	0.0830300412921	0.815222967031	144	0.0704545941739	0.82063455724
104	0.0826029733287	0.814691853537	145	0.0703556899463	0.824015021472
105	0.0822443217399	0.815398333895	146	0.0700228787103	0.821866827871
106	0.0819476076909	0.817235264322	147	0.0698354088134	0.823071129333
107	0.0815031219958	0.816020259504	148	0.0696144648715	0.82343508479
108	0.0811631657092	0.816789950013	149	0.0693635312446	0.82303315677
109	0.0808168363959	0.8173326791	150	0.0691947055768	0.824528486205
110	0.0804738966813	0.817845787842	151	0.0689504254511	0.824175161299
111	0.0802236160625	0.820155346445	152	0.0687337589632	0.824427467965
112	0.0799777581779	0.822479627533	153	0.068571090602	0.825928054977
113	0.079627127805	0.822563091782	154	0.0683384841161	0.825695802535
114	0.0793265031038	0.823588256183	155	0.068185250235	0.827334718217
115	0.0789376473447	0.822687448328	156	0.0679329422163	0.826521435605
116	0.0785583577702	0.821885758988	157	0.0677750998037	0.82795866932
117	0.0782320032452	0.822097708992	158	0.0676273800928	0.829604094682
118	0.0780038239026	0.824294624348	159	0.0674128925903	0.82956748828
119	0.0775963710114	0.822618471252	160	0.0672687341651	0.831218436479
120	0.0771012191108	0.818978329185	161	0.0670518246602	0.831028180762

Table 3: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular octagon for $162 \leq N \leq 200$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
162	0.0668048586906	0.830041464192	182	0.062919179177	0.827191681823
163	0.0665493846647	0.828789741239	183	0.0627464191781	0.8271754885
164	0.0663535412478	0.828973664303	184	0.0625281410955	0.825919143145
165	0.066131868153	0.828465066716	185	0.062437728452	0.828008111852
166	0.0659320815078	0.828457693978	186	0.0622830711706	0.828364840059
167	0.0656695854365	0.826825180506	187	0.0620672604686	0.82705698558
168	0.0655022148566	0.827541774161	188	0.0620266161641	0.830391129553
169	0.0652592031759	0.826302205405	189	0.0618883962705	0.831091682202
170	0.0651567400347	0.828583517359	190	0.0616292276176	0.828506127225
171	0.0649166300244	0.827326084491	191	0.061510565173	0.829662529065
172	0.064644862188	0.825211266504	192	0.0613907365404	0.830760024369
173	0.0645350389496	0.827191246615	193	0.061183787554	0.829466211188
174	0.0643152412644	0.826315174923	194	0.0610685383571	0.830625873237
175	0.0642090821886	0.828322859341	195	0.0610040411512	0.833144815235
176	0.0640030553876	0.827718678126	196	0.0607415401628	0.830226028088
177	0.0637765933396	0.826541330886	197	0.0605954530659	0.830452838879
178	0.0636378728685	0.827599054017	198	0.0604983139116	0.831994405908
179	0.0634452712328	0.827218467888	199	0.060335979644	0.831714910622
180	0.063204257793	0.825531882398	200	0.0601861141218	0.831747067093
181	0.0630483280333	0.826027292518			

Figure 1: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 2: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 3: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 4: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 5: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 6: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 7: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 8: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 9: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 10: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 11: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 12: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 13: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 14: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 15: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 16: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 17: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

3 Voronoi diagrams

We report the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations of section 2. We use the same color scheme as before, where the colors of each cell depends on the number of sides. One can assign a topological charge to the cell, depending on the number of sides of the cell and on the location of the cell: for internal cells, the topological charge is $q_{int} = 6 - \ell$, where ℓ is the number of sides, while for cells on the border $q_{border} = 5 - \ell$. Vertices from which emanate more than three lines carry a topological charge $q_{vert} = -2(n - 3)$, where n is the number of lines.

The Euler theorem of topology requires that the sum of all topological charges be equal to 6, regardless of the complexity of the configuration, but it does not forbid changing a number of cells with the same number of cells with different individual topological charges as long as the total charge is kept the same. For example, one could substitute two hexagonal internal cells with a pair consisting of a pentagonal and heptagonal cells. See [1] for a more detailed discussion.

Figure 18: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 19: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 20: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 21: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 22: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 23: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 24: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 25: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 26: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 27: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 28: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 29: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 30: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 31: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 32: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 33: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 34: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular octagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

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References

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